

THE ROLE OF VARIOUS OPTIONS FOR ARTIFICIAL NUTRITION IN ACUTE PANCREATITIS

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ABSTRACT

Artificial nutrition is an inherent part of management in acute pancreatitis. However, there is no consensus regarding the optimal time of the commencement of feeding in these patients. Our aim was to compare the effect of enteral v. parenteral nutrition with regard to the time points when they were administered in the randomised controlled trials.

Artificial nutrition has been regarded as an important component in the treatment of patients with acute pancreatitis⁽¹⁻³⁾. However, while parenteral nutrition had a major weight in artificial nutrition during the 1970s–1990s, the last decade was characterised by a gradual shift in nutritional management towards enteral nutrition. Three systematic reviews, which incorporated the data from available randomised controlled trials (RCT) on enteral v. parenteral nutrition in acute pancreatitis, have consistently confirmed this change and have shown a statistically significant reduction of infectious complications with the use of enteral nutrition⁽⁴⁻⁶⁾. Moreover, a recent meta-analysis, confined to RCT on patients with severe acute pancreatitis,

revealed a significantly reduced mortality in patients received enteral over parenteral nutrition⁽⁷⁾.

At the same time, the mechanism of such a beneficial effect of enteral nutrition is not entirely understandable^(8,9). At least in part, the timing of nutrition might have an influence on the results observed. In general, it is supposed that enteral nutrition contributes to the maintenance of the intestinal barrier function and may prevent bacterial translocation from the lumen^(10,11). Thereby, intuitively it seems logical to commence enteral nutrition early in the course of acute pancreatitis^(2,12). However, whereas some authors advocate the early start of nutrition within the hours after hospital

admission⁽¹²⁻¹⁴⁾, others prefer a wait-and-see policy, when the commencement of enteral feeding may be postponed for up to 17 d after admission to hospital⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁷⁾. So, until now the optimal time frameworks for the initiation of feeding in patients with acute pancreatitis have not yet been investigated. Therefore, we aimed at conducting a systematic review of RCT on enteral v. parenteral nutrition in patients with acute pancreatitis to define whether the time of the commencement of nutrition has an influence on the risk of clinically meaningful outcomes such as multiple organ failure, pancreatic infectious complications and mortality.

Methods

Study selection

We performed an electronic search for publications between 1950 and 1 March 2008, using the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, MEDLINE and Science Citation Index. The search was restricted to human studies that were published in English, French, German, Russian, Spanish or Dutch.

The terms used for the search in the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials and Science Citation Index were: 'acute pancreatitis' and 'enteral nutrition' or 'parenteral nutrition' and 'randomised trial'. The terms used for the search in MEDLINE were: 'pancreatitis' (medical subject heading (MeSH)) and 'enteral nutrition' (MeSH) or 'parenteral nutrition' (MeSH)

or 'parenteral nutrition, total' (MeSH) and 'randomised controlled trials' (publication type). Reference lists of all available published RCT and reviews on nutrition in acute pancreatitis were cross-checked manually to ensure that all applicable papers were included. Additionally, the abstracts of major gastroenterology congresses were also searched manually.

Each potentially relevant RCT was assessed for inclusion independently by two reviewers. Differences in opinion between the reviewers were resolved by consensus. Accepted interventions included enteral nutrition v. parenteral nutrition in acute pancreatitis. Only studies that reported the timing of the initiation of the nutrition protocol and the data on at least two of the three most clinically meaningful outcomes (multiple organ failure, pancreatic infectious complications and mortality) were considered.

Data extraction and quality assessment

Two reviewers, by means of a standardised data collection form, independently extracted general trial information, data on the study quality, details of nutrition protocols, including the timing of feeding start, and outcome data. Outcome variables included in the meta-analysis were: multiple organ failure, pancreatic infectious complications and mortality. The Jadad scale⁽¹⁸⁾ was used to assess the following aspects of the study quality: randomisation, double-blinding,

withdrawals and drop-outs (minimum total score 0, maximum total score 5). An RCT with a score higher than 2 was considered as an RCT of good quality⁽¹⁹⁾.

Statistical analysis

Analyses were done using the computer program Review Manager (version 4.2 for Windows; The Nordic Cochrane Centre, The Cochrane Collaboration, 2003, Copenhagen, Denmark). Pooled risk ratios (RR) and 95 % CI were calculated using a random-effects model. RR values of >1.0 represented an advantage for the enteral nutrition group compared with the parenteral nutrition group. The I^2 test and χ^2 test were used for the evaluation of statistical heterogeneity between included trials. A value of the I^2 measure more than 25 % and P value of the χ^2 test lower than 0.1 were considered to denote the presence of statistically significant heterogeneity between included RCT⁽²⁰⁾. Publication bias was assessed by the funnel plot method of Egger's test⁽²¹⁾.

Predefined stratified analyses were performed to evaluate the difference in RR between trials on early v. delayed nutrition. The time of nutrition commencement in each RCT was applied to the certain time points (24 h and 48 h after admission) and the corresponding study was assigned to either early or delayed group with regard to that time point. The estimated interaction effect was calculated as a ratio of RR for early and delayed nutrition. The significance of this effect

was assessed by using the test of interaction⁽²²⁾. P values less than 0.05 were considered to be significant.

Results

A total of 268 reports were screened and eleven RCT met our inclusion criteria (Fig. 1). Ten reports were available as full-text papers^(14-16,23-29) and one was published in abstract form only⁽³⁰⁾. Three (27 %) trials were published before the year 2000⁽²³⁻²⁵⁾. With regard to disease severity, seven of eleven trials incorporated solely patients with severe acute pancreatitis^(14,16,24,27-30), whereas the patient population consisted of both patients with mild and severe acute pancreatitis in four trials^(15,23,25,26).

Regarding methodological quality characteristics, although all trials reported a statement on randomisation, the treatment assignment method was not described in three RCT (27 %)^(15,23,30). Double-blinding was not possible due to the nature of the interventions. The description of withdrawals and drop-outs was reported in ten (91 %) RCT. A Jadad score of higher than 2 was attributed to six (55 %) trials^(14,16,24,27-29). The included studies comprised a total of 451 patients (214 patients received enteral nutrition and 237 patients received parenteral nutrition), ranging from seventeen to eighty-nine. Table 1 shows the study characteristics of RCT included in the systematic review. The data on study outcomes in each trial are presented in Table 2.

The nutrition protocol was initiated within 24 h of admission in four RCT and after 24 h in seven studies. With regard to this time point, the former was considered as 'early' nutrition and the latter as 'delayed' nutrition. Having applied this stratification, delayed nutrition, when compared with early nutrition, resulted in a greater risk reduction of pancreatic infectious complications (Fig. 2), but not multiple organ failure and mortality in patients with both mild and severe acute pancreatitis (Table 3). The test of interaction was non-significant in all comparisons. Heterogeneity between study results in these analyses was entirely attributable to random variation (I^2 0 %). When only patients from trials on severe acute pancreatitis were considered, delayed nutrition, in comparison with early nutrition, resulted in a reduction of risks for pancreatic infectious complications, multiple organ failure and mortality (Table 3). The test of interaction was non-significant. The early nutrition group had a

moderate heterogeneity in regard to pancreatic complications (I^2 35 %) and mortality (I^2 65 %), but not multiple organ failure (I^2 0 %).

The nutrition protocol was initiated within 48 h of admission in seven RCT and after 48 h in four studies. With regard to this time point, the former was considered as 'early' nutrition and the latter as 'delayed' nutrition. Having applied this stratification, delayed nutrition, when compared with early nutrition, resulted in a greater reduction of the risks for pancreatic infectious complications (Fig. 3), but not multiple organ failure and mortality in patients with both mild and severe acute pancreatitis (Table 3). The test of interaction was non-significant. Heterogeneity between study results in these analyses was mainly attributable to random variation (I^2 0, 0 and 21 % for multiple organ failure, pancreatic infectious complications and mortality, respectively). In trials that incorporated exclusively patients with severe Artificial nutrition and acute pancreatitis

Fig. 1. Selection of eligible randomised controlled trials.

acute pancreatitis, delayed nutrition, in comparison with early nutrition, resulted in a greater reduction of risks for pancreatic infectious complications, multiple organ failure and mortality (Table 3). The test of interaction was non-significant in all comparisons. Heterogeneity between the study results in regard to multiple organ failure, pancreatic infectious complications and mortality was low (I^2 0, 0 and 23 %, respectively).

Discussion

In line with the results of previous meta-analyses⁽⁴⁻⁸⁾ on enteral v. parenteral nutrition in acute pancreatitis, the present

Table 1. Study characteristics meta-analysis demonstrates the benefit of enteral nutrition in terms of risk reduction of infectious complications and mortality.

For the first time, it shows a statistically significant risk reduction of multiple organ failure in patients who received enteral over parenteral nutrition. These benefits were especially pronounced in patients with severe acute pancreatitis.

CONCLUSION

Another important finding of the present meta-analysis is that the timing of nutrition in the analysed trials might affect the clinical outcomes. Namely, the difference in the efficacy between enteral and parenteral nutrition is clearly evident in patients with an early (within 24 or 48 h after admission).

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